

Oxytetracycline as a New Analytical Reagent for the Spectrophotometric Determination of Boron

G. L. NARAYANA

Department of Chemistry, Jawahar Bharati, Kavali-524 202

Manuscript received 17 November 1977, revised 2 March 1981, accepted 30 May 1984

Oxytetracycline hydrochloride, Terramycin, is introduced as a new reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of trace quantities of boron in concentrated sulphuric acid medium. The reagent has an absorption maximum at 430 nm, and that of the boron complex at 520 nm. The coloured system conformed to Beer's law between 2 and 10 μg of boron at 520 nm. The molar absorptivity calculated on the basis of boron is 10,800 $\text{l mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$. The composition of the complex has been shown to be 1 : 1 both by the slope ratio and molar ratio methods.

THE tetracycline group of antibiotics contain multifunctional groups in their molecules which are responsible for the formation of several complexes with different metal ions. The behaviour of tetracycline and its analogues towards metal ions has been the subject of numerous investigations. Complex formation of Terramycin with metal ions was studied¹ with Fe^{3+} , Fe^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} . The complexes were found to be 1 : 1 and 2 : 1, ligand to metal. Formation of coloured complexes of the metal ions Th^{4+} , Zr^{4+} , Al^{3+} , UO_2^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Mg^{2+} with oxytetracycline was reported². The absorption curves of these complexes and the ratio of metal to ligand were given, especially the chelates of zirconium and thorium were found to be stable. The ability of complexation of oxytetracycline with ferric iron³, uranyl⁴, molybdate⁵, and tungstate⁶ has been used for the photometric determination of the antibiotic. The complex formation with magnesium⁷ was used for the fluorimetric determination of oxytetracycline.

The coloured complexes of boron with oxytetracycline in concentrated sulphuric acid reported⁸ the formation of two complexes with absorption maxima at 480 and 570 nm, and both the complexes to be 1 : 1 boron to ligand. The formation constant was reported as 1.5 (log K). The ligand in these chelates was anhydroxy-tetracycline formed due to the dehydration of oxytetracycline by sulphuric acid. The complexation of boron was studied⁹ with tetracycline, chlorotetracycline¹⁰, and 7-chloro-6-demethyl tetracycline in concentrated sulphuric acid for the spectrophotometric determination of boron. The present study reports the use of oxytetracycline for the spectrophotometric determination of boron.

Oxytetracycline hydrochloride, trade name Terramycin, dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with cherry red colour which turns to light orange

within ten minutes in dilute solutions. Addition of boric acid changes the colour to red. With a reagent concentration of 200 μg in 5 ml sulphuric acid the colour was golden yellow and that of the test rose red with less than 1 μg boron. In sulphuric acid solution oxytetracycline had an absorption maximum at 430 nm, and the boron complex at 520 nm. Linear relationship was found between 2-10 μg boron and absorbancies for the reagent concentration used. The molar absorptivity of the coloured product calculated on the basis of boron was found to be 10,800 $\text{l mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$.

Experimental

Oxytetracycline hydrochloride powder from the Terramycin capsule was weighed and dissolved in definite volume of concentrated sulphuric acid. Lower concentrations were prepared from this solution. The reagent solutions were prepared on each day.

98 per cent sulphuric acid ($d=1.84$) and boric acid (AnalaR, B.D.H.) were used. 0.5716 g of boric acid was dissolved in sulphuric acid and made upto 100 ml (1 ml=1.0 mg boron). Lower concentrations of boron were prepared by successive dilution of the stock solution with sulphuric acid.

Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20 Regulated Model with test tubes (outside diameter 13 cm) were used for the absorbance measurements. Ground glass stoppered test tubes of about of 42 ml capacity were used for the development of colour, and to minimize contamination were soaked for eighteen days in concentrated hydrochloric acid¹¹ and washed thoroughly with deionized water.

The volume of an aliquot of boron, as boric acid, (upto 10 μg of boron) in concentrated sulphuric acid was adjusted to 8 ml with the acid, and 2 ml of oxytetracycline hydrochloride (1.0 mg) in sulphuric

acid was added. The absorbance measurements were made after one hour at 520 nm in the spectrophotometer against a reagent blank prepared at the time of the test. Measurements can be made upto 5 h after the addition of the reagent.

Results and Discussion

Beer's law and stability of colour : Beer's law was obeyed over the range of 2 to 10 μg of boron in 10 ml solution for 1.0 mg of the reagent. Duplicate determinations were carried out at two different times. Least square analysis of the results gave a slope of 0.0744 absorbance for one microgram of boron, the absorbancies at 2 μg and 10 μg of boron being 0.175 and 0.757, respectively.

The absorbance of the boron-reagent complex remained constant from 45 min to 5h after the development of colour. After 22 h 25% decrease in the absorbancies was found. However, no measurements was made between 5 and 22 h. The absorbance of the complex depends on the concentration of the acid and are reproducible in 98% sulphuric acid.

A precision study was carried out by taking 12 replicate measurements on solutions containing 6 μg of boron using the procedure. The mean absorbance, standard deviation, and relative standard deviation (%) were 0.478, 0.0222 and 4.65, respectively.

Interference due to foreign ions : The solution used for the interference study contained 5 mg of the cation or anion in 1 ml sulphuric acid, so that when 2.0 ml was used, the amount of ion was approximately 1000 fold over the amount of boron taken. The solubilities of the salt were an important limitation. In other cases saturated solutions of the salts at room temperature (32°) in concentrated sulphuric acid were used. In the case of sulphates of ammonium, potassium and sodium, 200 mg of salt was used in 8 ml of the solution of boron (10 μg). Interference due to various ions were made on 10 μg of boron as reference. Saturated solutions (2.0 ml) of Al^{3+} , Ce^{4+} , Cu^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Sb^{3+} , Sn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} caused no interference. No interference was caused by 10 mg of each of As (as arsenate), Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} , and 200 mg of ammonium sulphate, potassium sulphate and sodium sulphate. 10 mg of oxalate, acetate, ferrocyanide caused no interference. Slight interference was caused by saturated solution (2.0 ml) of ferricyanide. Serious interference was caused by Ba^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , molybdate, phosphate, fluoride and nitrate ions.

The molar absorptivities of hydroxy anthraquinone derivatives which also require a high concentration of sulphuric acid and are in wide usage in the spectrophotometric determination of boron are given in Table 1, for comparison of the sensitivity of the new reagent including chlorotetracycline.

TABLE 1

Reagent	Molar absorptivity* ($\text{l mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	Reference
Carmine	5,400	12
Tetrabromovhryszin	12,000	13
Diaminoanthrarufin	4,300	14
Diaminochryszin	5,100	14
Dinitroanthrarufin	4,900	14
Tribromoanthrarufin	10,800	14
Chlorotetracycline	5,800	10
Oxytetracycline	10,800	—

*Calculated from the spectrophotometric sensitivities given in the references.

Composition of the complex : To study the composition of the complex the slope ratio¹⁵ and the molar ratio¹⁶ methods were used. Both the methods indicated the formation of 1 : 1 as reported⁶.

Absorbances were measured on solutions containing 1.0 mg of boron and 0.25 to 2.0 micromole of oxytetracycline hydrochloride in 10 ml solution. The slope of the straight line was found to be 0.6582 by the method of least squares. Similar experiments were carried out on solutions containing 4 mg oxytetracycline hydrochloride and 0.20 to 1.40 micromole of boron and gave a slope of 0.6872. The slope ratio was found to be 1 : 1 within experimental errors.

Absorbance measurements carried out on 1.844 micromole of the reagent with varying amounts of boron indicated the formation of 1 : 1 complex. The mole ratio of ligand to boron was varied between 6 : 1 to 1 : 20.

Nature of the complex : From the spectral curves (Fig. 1) it is evident that oxytetracycline absorbs appreciably at 510-520 nm. It appears that a single complex of boron and oxytetracycline in concentrated sulphuric acid is formed under the experimental conditions. The absorption maximum of the reagent with boron occurs at 510 nm and there has been a slight shift of the absorption peak to 520 nm with excess of the reagent. The formation of two complexes with absorption maxima at 480 nm and 570 nm was reported⁶. The second complex was, however, formed on standing or heating the solution of boron and oxytetracycline. In the present investigation the complex formed was studied within five hours and at room temperature and no absorption peak was observed at 570 nm. The same study⁶ further reported the absorption maximum at 495 nm for the complex formed between boric acid dehydrated with fuming sulphuric acid and oxytetracycline in sulphuric acid solution. The complex formed in the present investigation might be similar to that of the latter reported complex. The observed difference in the absorption maxima of these two complexes might possibly be due to the cumulative effect of concentration of sulphuric acid, temperature and concentration of reagents. The ratio of boron to ligand

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra. I. Oxytetracycline hydrochloride (500 μ g in 10 ml) in conc. H_2SO_4 ; II. Boron complex (500 μ g + 175 μ g boron in 10 ml) in conc. H_2SO_4 ; III. Complex with excess of reagent (12 μ g boron + 1.0 mg reagent in 10 ml) and IV. Boron complex with excess of boron (solution of II used). (III and IV are against respective reagent blanks).

in the complex was 1 : 1. The ligand in the complex is the anhydro-oxytetracycline formed due to the dehydration by sulphuric acid. Oxytetracycline and its boron complex after keeping for two hours have the absorption maxima at 430 nm and 520 nm, respectively.

Acknowledgement

The author is indebted to Mr. D. Ramachandra Reddy, Rector, Jawahar Bharati, for financial assistance and for providing laboratory facilities.

References

1. A. ALBERT, *Nature*, 1953, 172, 201.
2. T. SAKAGUCHI, M. TOMA, T. YOSHIDA, H. OMURA and H. TAKASU, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. (Tokyo)*, 1958, 6, 1.
3. A. MIZSEI and A. SZABO, *Acta Pharm. Hung.*, 1955, 25, 167.
4. A. FIEBIG, S. JANICKI and H. WASIAK, *Dtsches. Warzt.*, 1965, 17, 81.
5. K. KAKEMI, T. UNO and M. SAMEJIMA, *J. Pharm. Soc. Jpn.*, 1955, 75, 192.
6. K. TERAI, *Osaka Shritsu Daigaku Igaku Zasshi*, 1959, 8, 481.
7. K. H. IBSEN, R. L. SAUNDERS and M. R. URIST, *Anal. Biochem.*, 1963, 5, 505.
8. T. SAKAGUCHI, K. SEKIGUCHI, A. HANAKI and A. SAITO, *Yakugaku Zasshi*, 1959, 79, 461 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1959, 53, 14811).
9. G. LAKSHMINARAYANA, Ph.D. Thesis, Sri Venkateswara University, Tirupati, 1973.
10. G. L. NARAYANA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 417.
11. M. L. JACKSON, "Soil Chemical Analysis", Prentice-Hall India, New Delhi, 1967, p. 376.
12. J. T. HATCHER and L. V. WILCOX, *Anal. Chem.*, 1950, 22, 567.
13. J. H. YOE and R. L. GROB, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, 26, 1465.
14. E. C. COGBILL and J. H. YOE, *Anal. Chem.*, 1957, 29, 1251.
15. A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 1251.
16. J. H. YOE and A. I. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111.